

Kinetics and mechanism of reverse water-gas shift reaction on a Cu-ZnO-Al₂O₃ catalyst

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The kinetic data of reverse water-gas shift reaction on a Cu-ZnO-Al₂O₃ catalyst have been determined by means of a perfectly stirred catalytic reactor. Hougen-Watson method has been applied in analysis of kinetic data while in processing of experimental data use has been made of Powel's algorithm. From among the possible mechanisms of the process, Rideal-Eley's one is prevalingly accepted; according to this mechanism the carbon dioxide adsorbed on catalyst surface reacts with the hydrogen in gas phase. The activation energy of the process amounts to 61.03 kJ mol⁻¹.

Cu-ZnO-Al₂O₃ is among the catalysts involved in the chain of catalytic processes of hydrogen purification at ammonia synthesis. Following methane catalytic reformation with steam, the resulting carbon monoxide is converted into carbon dioxide in two steps. In the first step, most of the carbon monoxide is converted (with water vapour) usually on oxidic iron-chromium catalysts at temperatures below 720 K; in the second step, the carbon monoxide conversion is completed on catalysts which, in active state, contain dispersed metallic copper, together with ZnO and Al₂O₃ as well as other components; the catalytic process occurs at 573 K (hence the low temperature catalyst name assigned to these catalysts)¹.

The reverse water-gas shift reaction is the reaction of carbon dioxide with hydrogen which is accelerated by Cu-ZnO-Al₂O₃ catalyst as well. While the direct reaction was extensively studied², that of carbon dioxide with hydrogen,

has enjoyed very little attention³, though it is also interesting. Reaction (1) is much easier to control than the conversion reaction and the results of a study on its unfolding in presence of a certain catalyst supply informations upon the quality of the catalyst and the process of water-gas shift reaction which represents an efficient method of catalyst production control. Sometimes reaction (1) is undesirably present in catalytic processes (with other catalysts) in presence of carbon dioxide and hydrogen, yet in absence of water.

Reaction mechanisms and possible kinetic models :

Use has been made of Hougen-Watson method to establish the reverse water-gas shift reaction on Cu-ZnO-Al₂O₃

catalyst. The experimental and mathematical methods are described elsewhere⁴.

Starting up from the reaction, $\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$, one can imagine several possible mechanisms of catalytic reaction whose Hougen-Watson type equations can be written as

In all reaction mechanisms developed it was assumed that carbon dioxide reacts with the hydrogen adsorbed on catalyst surface (models I-IV) or in gaseous state (models V-VIII), only in adsorbed state. The carbon monoxide and water result from the reaction either adsorbed or not on the active centres (denoted by L) on catalyst surface. The reaction mechanisms which assume that the carbon dioxide reacts in gaseous state were disregarded because the carbon dioxide dipolar molecule is readily adsorbed on active metallic surfaces. In the equations of reaction rate that follows, the subscripts of physical quantities have the following significances : 1-carbon dioxide, 2-hydrogen, 3-carbon monoxide, 4-water and 5-nitrogen. The reaction rate equations should take account of the role of the 'inert' gas involved in the process. If one assumes that the inert gas does not influence the catalytic process, the expressions of reaction rate

(according to Hougen-Watson method) for the reaction mechanisms (I)-(VIII) are as follows :

$$r = \frac{kK_1K_2p_1p_2}{(1 + K_1p_1 + K_2p_2)^2} \quad (\text{E Ia})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1K_2p_1p_2}{(1 + K_1p_1 + K_2p_2 + K_3p_3)^2} \quad (\text{E IIa})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1K_2p_1p_2}{(1 + K_1p_1 + K_2p_2 + K_4p_4)^2} \quad (\text{E IIIa})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1K_2p_1p_2}{(1 + K_1p_1 + K_2p_2 + K_3p_3 + K_4p_4)^2} \quad (\text{E IVa})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1p_1}{1 + K_1p_1} \quad (\text{E Va})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1p_1}{1 + K_1p_1 + K_3p_3} \quad (\text{E VIa})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1p_1}{1 + K_1p_1 + K_4p_4} \quad (\text{E VIIa})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1p_1}{(1 + K_1p_1 + K_3p_3 + K_4p_4)^2} \quad (\text{E VIIIa})$$

However, if one assumes that some active centres on catalyst surface are occupied by inert gas molecules (in case of the process under study nitrogen) the reaction rate equations should include the contribution of the inert gas to slowing down the reaction :

$$r = \frac{kK_1K_2p_1p_2}{(1 + K_1p_1 + K_2p_2 + K_3p_3)^3} \quad (\text{E Ib})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1K_2p_1p_2}{(1 + K_1p_1 + K_2p_2 + K_3p_3 + K_5p_5)^3} \quad (\text{E IIb})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1K_2p_1p_2}{(1 + K_1p_1 + K_2p_2 + K_4p_4 + K_5p_5)^3} \quad (\text{E IIIb})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1K_2p_1p_2}{(1 + K_1p_1 + K_2p_2 + K_3p_3 + K_4p_4 + K_5p_5)^3} \quad (\text{E IVb})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1p_1}{(1 + K_1p_1 + K_3p_3)^2} \quad (\text{E Vb})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1p_1}{(1 + K_1p_1 + K_3p_3 + K_5p_5)^2} \quad (\text{E VIb})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1p_1}{(1 + K_1p_1 + K_4p_4 + K_5p_5)^2} \quad (\text{E VIIb})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1p_1}{(1 + K_1p_1 + K_3p_3 + K_4p_4 + K_5p_5)^3} \quad (\text{E VIIIb})$$

The quantities p_j stand for partial pressures of gases. The analytical expressions of reaction rate constant (k) and of adsorption equilibrium constants (K_j) discussed in the previous contribution⁴, are

$$k = \exp\left[\frac{\Delta S^\circ}{R}\right] \cdot \exp\left[-\frac{\Delta E}{RT}\right] \quad (2)$$

where ΔS° stands for the entropy variation in the (chemical) activation process, and E for the activation energy of chemical reaction.

$$K_j = \exp\left[\frac{-\Delta G^\circ}{RT}\right] = \exp\left[\frac{\Delta S_j^\circ}{R}\right] \cdot \exp\left[-\frac{\Delta H_j^\circ}{RT}\right] \quad (3)$$

where ΔG_j° , ΔS_j° and ΔH_j° are the variations of adsorption standard free energies, entropies and enthalpies, respectively; $R = 8.31 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ is the universal gas constant and T the absolute temperature.

In order that the parameters in eqns. (2) and (3) have a physical significance, they should have the following signs

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta S^\circ &\text{-positive; } E\text{-positive (refers to chemical reaction)} \\ \Delta S_j^\circ &\text{-negative; } \Delta H_j^\circ\text{-negative (refers to adsorption equilibrium)} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The values of standard entropy in gaseous state S_g° of the participants in the catalytic process are⁵ : CO₂, 213.69; H₂, 130.61; CO, 197.45; H₂O, 188.78; N₂, 191.55 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹.

Before establishing the model which approximates best the actual mechanism of catalytic process one has to check if Boudart criteria⁴ are or are not observed, they evaluate the physical significance of the parameters estimated in the framework of a model. The four Boudart criteria (when the entropies are expressed in J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ and the enthalpies in J mol⁻¹ while $\nu \neq 0$) are

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad &\Delta S_j^\circ \text{ should be negative} \\ \text{(ii)} \quad &|\Delta S_j^\circ| < S_{\text{g}}^\circ \\ \text{(iii)} \quad &|\Delta S_j^\circ| > 41.85 \\ \text{(iv)} \quad &-\Delta S_j^\circ < 51.057 - 0.0014 \Delta H_j^\circ \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Results and Discussion

The results of A-E experiments, numbered from 1 to 30, in the sequence of runs are given in Table 1. Table 1 lists the experimental reaction rates (r) expressed in moles of CO₂ transformed in 1 h per g of catalyst. Use has been made of replica measurements to establish the relative error

Table 1. Steady state parameters

Run no.	$r \times 10^3$ mol h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹	T K	P ₁ atm	P ₂ atm	P ₃ atm	P ₄ atm	P ₅ atm
1	1.01	506	0.0986	0.8283	0.0074	0.0074	0.0583
2	1.42	516	0.0955	0.8252	0.0105	0.0105	0.0583
3	2.39	534	0.0883	0.8180	0.0177	0.0177	0.0583
4	3.06	545	0.0883	0.8130	0.0227	0.0227	0.0583
5	3.68	555	0.0788	0.8085	0.0272	0.0272	0.0583
6	4.42	568	0.0733	0.8030	0.0327	0.0327	0.0583
7	1.11	504	0.1272	0.8032	0.0082	0.0082	0.0532
8	1.34	509	0.1255	0.8015	0.0099	0.0099	0.0532
9	2.18	526	0.1193	0.7953	0.0161	0.0161	0.0532
10	3.13	542	0.1123	0.7883	0.0232	0.0232	0.0532
11	3.71	552	0.1080	0.7840	0.0274	0.0274	0.0532
12	4.47	565	0.1023	0.7783	0.0331	0.0331	0.0532
13	1.43	508	0.1424	0.7844	0.0106	0.0106	0.0520
14	1.75	515	0.1401	0.7821	0.0129	0.0129	0.0520
15	2.40	527	0.1352	0.7772	0.0178	0.0178	0.0520
16	3.17	540	0.1296	0.7716	0.0234	0.0234	0.0520
17	3.83	551	0.1246	0.7666	0.0284	0.0284	0.0520
18	4.96	571	0.1163	0.7583	0.0367	0.0367	0.0520
19	1.54	505	0.1780	0.7500	0.0114	0.0114	0.0492
20	2.02	515	0.1744	0.7464	0.0150	0.0150	0.0492
21	3.06	533	0.1667	0.7387	0.0227	0.0227	0.0492
22	3.59	542	0.1628	0.7348	0.0266	0.0266	0.0492
23	4.39	556	0.1569	0.7289	0.0325	0.0325	0.0492
24	5.26	571	0.1505	0.7225	0.0389	0.0389	0.0492
25	1.52	498	0.2121	0.6994	0.0113	0.0113	0.0659
26	2.05	510	0.2082	0.6955	0.0152	0.0152	0.0659
27	2.62	520	0.2040	0.6913	0.0194	0.0194	0.0659
28	3.50	534	0.1975	0.6848	0.0259	0.0259	0.0659
19	4.15	546	0.1927	0.6800	0.0307	0.0307	0.0659
30	5.27	566	0.1844	0.6717	0.0390	0.0390	0.0659

in determination of reaction rate : about 6×10^{-2} . The experimental data were used in calculation of the optimal values of the parameters only for eight equations of reaction rate which offer the mathematical description of (I), (IV), (V) and (VIII) reaction mechanisms. The remaining mechanisms, i.e. (II), (III), (VI) and (VII) could not have been described owing to the equal amounts of water and carbon monoxide resulted from the process; therefore, the mechanism accepted as real could not break the symmetry of the two components favouring one of them.

Objective functions were developed for Hougen-Watson type expressions still considered possible; these functions are equal to the sum of the squares of differences between the reaction rates calculated according to a kinetic model and the corresponding experimental values⁴,

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^{30} \left[\frac{\prod_{j=0}^m K_{ij}^{n_j} \prod_{j=1}^m p_{ij}^{n_j}}{\left(1 + \sum_{j=1}^s K_{ij} p_{ij}\right)^\alpha} - r_i \right]^2 \quad (6)$$

where K_{ij} is given by equation,

$$K_{ij} = \exp \left[\frac{\Delta S_j^0}{R} \right] \cdot \exp \left[-\frac{\Delta H_j^0}{RT_i} \right] \quad (7)$$

In eqns. (6) and (7), $j = 0$ refers to the chemical reaction, while j from 1 to 5 stands for CO₂, H₂, CO, H₂O and N₂, respectively. In eqn. (6), $m = 2$, $n_0 = 1$, $n_1 = 1$, $n_2 = 1$ or zero; s and α take the values corresponding to analytical writing of eqns. (E Ia), (E IVa), (E Va), (E VIIIa), (E Ib), (E IVb), (E Vb) and (E VIIIb).

The parameters ΔS_j^0 and ΔH_j^0 are obtained by minimizing the objective function F , whenever the partial pressures (p_{ij}), the experimental rates (r_i) and the absolute temperatures (T_i) are known and their values are acceptable :

$$\Delta S_0^0 (\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}) \in [16; 84];$$

$$E = \Delta H_0^0 (\text{J mol}^{-1}) \in [12000; 105000];$$

$$\Delta S_j^0 (\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}) \in [-100; -12]; j \neq 0$$

$$\Delta H_j^0 (\text{J mol}^{-1}) \in [-55000; -8000]; j \neq 0$$

Use has been made of modified Powell algorithm to minimize the objective function F^4 . The vector x_0 was built up from the preliminarily estimated values of the parameters :

$$\Delta S_0^0 = 41.85 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$$

$$E = 41850 \text{ J mol}^{-1}$$

$$\Delta S_j^0 = -41.85 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}; j \neq 0$$

$$\Delta H_j^0 = -33480 \text{ J mol}^{-1}; j \neq 0$$

The minimizing of objective function for the eight models of reaction rate equations, allowed the calculation of the optimal values of the parameters that describe the catalytic process under study as well as their standard deviations (Table 2). Table 3 lists the experimental reaction rates and the corresponding values calculated in terms of different kinetic models, making use of the optimal parameters in Table 2 (entropies and enthalpies of the process). The reaction rates are expressed in mol h⁻¹ g⁻¹ and are multiplied by 10³ to make writing simpler. A statistical evaluation of the kinetic models studied for experimental and calculated rates is given in Table 4; the minimum value of objective function $F(F_{\min})$, as well as the standard deviation (σ_r), and the relative deviation (ϵ_r) of the values calculated from the experimental ones. The value of relative deviation is less than

Table 2a. Optimal values and standard deviations of the parameters calculated for (E Ia), (E IVa), (E Va) and (E VIIIa) models of reaction rate

Parameter	E Ia model		E IVa model		E Va model		E VIIIa model	
	Value	Deviation	Value	Deviation	Value	Deviation	Value	Deviation
ΔS^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	73 95	0 28	55 11	0 29	66 81	0 47	66 74	0 47
E (J mol ⁻¹)	57277 10	98 68	48016 82	102 30	61030 15	165 30	55182 32	165 06
ΔS_1^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	-12 73	0 28	-12 73	0 29	-67 76	0 47	-12 73	0 47
ΔH_1^0 (J mol ⁻¹)	-17605 27	98 68	-21308 04	102 30	-50268 16	165 30	-12939 89	165 06
ΔS_2^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	-89 72	0 28	-75 18	0 29				
ΔH_2^0 (J mol ⁻¹)	-54401 16	98 68	-50272 02	102 30				
ΔS_3^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)			-14 93	0 29			-12 73	0 47
ΔH_3^0 (J mol ⁻¹)			-8372 01	102 30			-8371 35	165 06
ΔS_4^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)			-13 15	0 29			-23 42	0 47
ΔH_4^0 (J mol ⁻¹)			-8372 25	102 30			-8371 5	165 06

Table 2b. Optimal values and standard deviations of the parameters calculated for (E Ib), (E IVb), (E Vb) and (E VIIIb) models of reaction rate

Parameter	E Ib model		E IVb model		E Vb model		E VIIIb model	
	Value	Deviation	Value	Deviation	Value	Deviation	Value	Deviation
ΔS^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	47 16	0 23	62 45	0 26	44 27	0 48	49 22	0 50
E (J mol ⁻¹)	36158 88	82 76	39567 91	90 37	41964 23	169 86	42617 11	176 11
ΔS_1^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	-12 73	0 23	-12 73	0 26	-12 73	0 48	-12 73	0 50
ΔH_1^0 (J mol ⁻¹)	-14276 00	82 76	-17841 56	90 37	-13551 55	169 86	-10523 69	176 11
ΔS_2^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	-83 46	0 23	-75 63	0 26				
ΔH_2^0 (J mol ⁻¹)	-47818 35	82 76	-49203 88	90 37				
ΔS_3^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)			-13 68	0 26			-40 77	0 50
ΔH_3^0 (J mol ⁻¹)			-24502 17	90 37			-8371 35	176 11
ΔS_4^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)			-12 79	0 26			-16 62	0 50
ΔH_4^0 (J mol ⁻¹)			-21278 30	90 37			-8371 35	176 11
ΔS_5^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	-83 46	0 23	-83 46	0 26	-82 79	0 48	-83 46	0 50
ΔH_5^0 (J mol ⁻¹)	-8374 09	82 76	-10358 70	90 37	-50271 61	169 86	-47959 49	176 11

experimental error (6×10^{-2} , as previously evaluated) which confers consistency to the data obtained for the kinetic models studied.

Table 5 shows the results obtained making use of Boudart criteria⁴. Whenever a criterion is not verified NV appears in Table 5. It may be noted that symbol NV is absent only in case of (E Va) model. This model assumes that the catalytic reaction occurs between carbon dioxide adsorbed, hydrogen in gas phase and the resulting carbon monoxide and water are in gas phase. The catalytic process is not influenced by the presence of nitrogen in the gaseous mixture. One can state that mechanism (V) (model E Va for the reaction rate) of Rideal-Eley type is the actual mechanism which describes the unfolding of the catalytic process taking place on Cu-ZnO-Al₂O₃ catalyst. The accepted value of the activation energy of the process is 6.0 kJ mol⁻¹.

Conclusions : The kinetic data of reverse water-gas shift reaction on a Cu-ZnO-Al₂O₃ catalyst were analyzed making use of eight possible models of the process mechanism based on adsorption of molecular species on catalyst sur-

face area. Hougen-Watson type equations were developed for these models. The optimal kinetic parameters were calculated by minimizing some objective functions of sum of squares type. The actual catalytic process selected by means of Boudart criteria is of Rideal-Eley type. This mechanism considers that the adsorbed carbon dioxide reacts with the hydrogen from the gaseous phase, while the carbon monoxide and water resulted from the process lie in the gaseous phase.

Experimental

Catalyst preparation : The industrial catalyst studied was obtained by coprecipitation of Cu, Zn, Al nitrates with sodium carbonate and contained 30 CuO, 39 ZnO, 14 Al₂O₃, 2% graphite; 15% were calcination losses⁶ as water and CO₂.

Catalyst characterisation : The catalyst shaped as cylindrical sturdy tablets (6 mm dia and height) having average axial resistance approaching 850 kgf cm⁻² while the average radial resistance 70 kgf cm⁻¹ (WOLPERT, ZR 60/

Table 3a. Experimental and calculated reaction rates for (E Ia), (E IVa), (E Va) and (E VIIIa) models of reaction rate

Run no.	Exptl.	E Ia model	E IVa model	E Va model	E VIIIa model
1	1.01	1.04	1.04	1.06	1.06
2	1.42	1.44	1.44	1.50	1.48
3	2.39	2.37	2.36	2.42	2.38
4	3.06	3.00	2.99	3.04	3.00
5	3.68	3.60	3.59	3.61	3.57
6	4.42	4.32	4.32	4.30	4.29
7	1.11	1.15	1.16	1.16	1.17
8	1.34	1.37	1.37	1.39	1.39
9	2.18	2.20	2.19	2.21	2.20
10	3.13	3.13	3.12	3.13	3.11
11	3.71	3.71	3.70	3.70	3.69
12	4.47	4.49	4.49	4.47	4.47
13	1.43	1.46	1.46	1.46	1.47
14	1.75	1.77	1.77	1.77	1.77
15	2.40	2.41	2.41	2.40	2.40
16	3.17	3.17	3.16	3.16	3.14
17	3.83	3.85	3.84	3.83	3.82
18	4.96	5.03	5.03	5.01	5.04
19	1.54	1.54	1.56	1.52	1.53
20	2.02	2.02	2.03	1.99	1.99
21	3.06	3.05	3.05	3.01	3.00
22	3.59	3.59	3.58	3.55	3.54
23	4.39	4.43	4.42	4.41	4.41
24	5.26	5.34	5.34	5.36	5.40
25	1.52	1.49	1.51	1.44	1.45
26	2.05	2.01	2.02	1.95	1.96
27	2.62	2.56	2.57	2.50	2.50
28	3.50	3.41	3.42	3.36	3.36
29	4.15	4.09	4.09	4.07	4.06
30	5.27	5.27	5.28	5.35	5.36

Table 3b. Experimental and calculated reaction rates for (E Ib), (E IVb), (E Vb) and (E VIIIb) models of reaction rate

Run no.	Exptl.	E Ib model	E IVb model	E Vb model	VIIIb model
1	1.01	1.03	1.03	1.06	1.06
2	1.42	1.44	1.45	1.47	1.47
3	2.39	2.38	2.40	2.38	2.37
4	3.06	3.03	3.04	3.00	2.99
5	3.68	3.61	3.61	3.57	3.56
6	4.42	4.31	4.29	4.27	4.25
7	1.11	1.14	1.13	1.17	1.17
8	1.34	1.36	1.36	1.39	1.40
9	2.18	2.21	2.22	2.21	2.21
10	3.13	3.15	3.16	3.13	3.13

Table-3b (Contd.)

11	3.71	3.73	3.74	3.70	3.70
12	4.47	4.49	4.48	4.47	4.47
13	1.43	1.45	1.44	1.47	1.48
14	1.75	1.77	1.77	1.78	1.79
15	2.40	2.42	2.43	2.42	2.42
16	3.17	3.19	3.20	3.17	3.17
17	3.83	3.86	3.86	3.84	3.84
18	4.96	5.00	4.99	5.03	5.03
19	1.54	1.53	1.53	1.55	1.55
20	2.02	2.02	2.02	2.02	2.03
21	3.06	3.07	3.07	3.04	3.07
22	3.59	3.60	3.61	3.58	3.59
23	4.39	4.43	4.43	4.44	4.44
24	5.26	5.31	5.30	5.39	5.40
25	1.52	1.47	1.46	1.43	1.43
26	2.05	2.01	2.01	1.95	1.94
27	2.62	2.57	2.58	2.49	2.49
28	3.50	3.44	3.43	3.35	3.35
29	4.15	4.12	4.12	4.05	4.05
30	5.27	5.26	5.26	5.31	5.31

Table 4. Statistical evaluation of calculated reaction rates

Kinetic model	$10^7 F_{\min}$ $\text{mol}^2 \text{h}^{-2} \text{g}^{-2}$	$10^5 \sigma_r$ $\text{mol h}^{-1} \text{g}^{-1}$	$10^2 \epsilon_r$
E Ia	0.65	4.65	1.32
E IVa	0.58	4.41	1.35
E Va	1.22	6.37	2.11
E VIIIa	1.53	7.14	2.25
E Ib	0.43	3.79	1.17
E IVb	0.50	4.09	1.27
E Vb	1.50	7.08	2.16
E VIIIb	1.66	7.44	2.25

300). Application of mercury penetration porosimetry (porosimeter Carlo-Erba 70H) revealed the following parameters : apparent density, 2.367 g cm^{-3} ; pore volume, $0.293 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$; surface area, $68.879 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. The radius of most pores (51% of overall pore volume) was below 100 Å; about 30% of the overall pore volume consisted of pores whose radii range was 100–300 Å and only 20% had radii larger than 300 Å. Because internal diffusion should not be a determining step of reaction rate, the size of catalyst tablets should be less than 2 mm. The effective surface area of metallic copper in the catalyst was determined by Dvorak and Pasek method⁷; it applies gas chromatography to measurements of metallic copper surface area which results from the amount of nitrogen yielded by the chemisorptive decomposition of nitrogen protoxide on copper active surface. The fresh catalyst reduced with hydrogen at 523 K possessed

Table 5. Boudart criteria (BC) applied to the results

Model	BC	CO ₂	H ₂	CO	H ₂ O	N ₂
E Ia	(i)	-12 73	-89 72			
	(ii)	12 73 < 213 69	89 72 < 130 61			
	(iii)	12 73 < 41 85 NV	89 72 > 41 85			
	(iv)	12 73 < 75 70	89 72 < 127 22			
E IVa	(i)	-12 73	-75 18	-14 93	-13 15	
	(ii)	12 73 < 213 69	75 18 < 130 61	14 93 < 197 45	13 15 < 188 78	
	(iii)	12 73 < 41 85 NV	75 18 > 41 85	14 93 < 41 85 NV	13 15 < 41 85 NV	
	(iv)	12 73 < 80 89	75 18 < 121 44	14 93 < 62 78	13 15 < 62 78	
E Va	(i)	67 76				
	(ii)	67 76 < 213 69				
	(iii)	67 76 > 41 85				
	(iv)	67 76 < 121 43				
E VIIIa	(i)	-12 73		-12 73	-23 42	
	(ii)	12 73 < 213 69		12 73 < 197 45	23 42 < 188 78	
	(iii)	12 73 < 41 85 NV		12 73 < 41 85 NV	23 42 < 41 85 NV	
	(iv)	12 73 < 69 17		12 73 < 62 78	23 42 < 62 78	
E Ib	(i)	-12 73	-83 46			-83 46
	(ii)	12 73 < 213 69	83 46 < 130 61			83 46 < 191 55
	(iii)	12 73 < 41 85 NV	83 46 > 41 85			83 46 > 41 85
	(iv)	12 73 < 71 04	83 46 < 118 00			83 46 > 62 78 NV
E IVb	(i)	-12 73	-75 63	-13 68	-12 79	-83 46
	(ii)	12 73 < 213 69	75 63 < 130 61	13 68 < 197 45	12 79 < 188 78	83 46 < 119 55
	(iii)	12 73 < 41 85 NV	75 63 > 41 85	13 68 < 41 85 NV	12 79 < 41 85 NV	83 46 > 41 85
	(iv)	12 73 < 76 04	75 63 < 119 94	13 68 < 85 36	12 79 < 80 85	83 46 > 65 56 NV
E Vb	(i)	-12 73				-82 79
	(ii)	12 73 < 213 69				82 79 < 119 55
	(iii)	12 73 < 41 85 NV				82 79 > 41 85
	(iv)	12 73 < 70 03				82 79 < 121 44
E VIIIb	(i)	-12 73		-40 77	-16 62	-83 46
	(ii)	12 73 < 213 69		40 77 < 197 45	16 62 < 188 78	83 46 < 119 55
	(iii)	12 73 < 41 85 NV		40 77 < 41 85 NV	16 62 < 41 85 NV	83 46 > 41 85
	(iv)	12 73 < 65 79		40 77 < 62 78	16 62 < 62 78	83 46 < 118 20

Table 6. Composition of gas mixtures used for reactor feed (given in normal conditions of temperature and pressure)

Expt	Gas	Composition %	Flow l h ⁻¹	Flow × 10 ³ mol h ⁻¹
A	H ₂	83 57	5 01	207 06
	N ₂	5 83	0 35	14 45
	CO ₂	10 60	0 64	26 26
B	H ₂	81 14	4 87	201 04
	N ₂	5 32	0 32	13 18
	CO ₂	13 54	0 81	33 55
C	H ₂	79 50	4 77	196 98
	N ₂	5 20	0 31	12 88
	CO ₂	15 30	0 92	37 91
D	H ₂	76 14	4 57	188 65
	N ₂	4 92	0 29	12 19
	CO ₂	18 94	1 14	46 93
E	H ₂	71 07	4 26	176 09
	N ₂	6 59	0 40	16 33
	CO ₂	22 34	1 34	55 35

a copper effective surface area of 81.2 m² Cu/g Cu (16 m² Cu/g catalyst). After application of activity test the effective surface area became 63 m² Cu/g Cu (14 m² Cu/g catalyst). Possession of these data afforded calculation of the copper crystal average size 83 Å for fresh catalyst and 108 Å the one used in the testing of the activity.

The morphological and structural properties of the catalyst were determined by X-ray diffraction (diffractometer Philips PW 1140) and electron microscopy. The unreduced catalyst consisted of a CuO and ZnO mixture in advanced state of dispersion; they formed well shaped crystallites which yielded narrow and well separated X-ray diffraction maxima. The size of CuO crystallites was 50–55 Å, while that of ZnO 40–45 Å. On reduction of the fresh catalyst (which was not subjected to any activity test) copper crystallites showed up whose average size was 65 Å (ZnO crystallites slightly increased to 55 Å), while reactivation of the passivated catalyst (which was subjected to activity tests) rose the measured average size of Cu crystallites to 103 Å;

Table 7. Composition of gases after the reaction and the reaction rates

Run no.	Temp. K	Composition %					Flow, $\times 10^3$ mol h ⁻¹					Reaction rate, $\times 10^3$ mol h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹
		H ₂	N ₂	CO	CO ₂	H ₂ O	H ₂	N ₂	CO	CO ₂	H ₂ O	
Experiment A :												
1	506	82.83	5.83	0.74	9.86	0.74	205.22	14.44	1.84	24.42	1.84	1.01
2	516	82.52	5.83	1.05	9.51	1.05	204.22	14.44	2.60	23.66	2.60	1.42
3	534	81.80	5.83	1.77	8.83	1.77	202.68	14.44	4.38	21.88	4.38	2.39
4	545	81.30	5.83	2.27	8.33	2.27	201.45	14.44	5.62	20.65	5.62	3.06
5	555	80.85	5.83	2.72	7.88	2.72	200.31	14.44	6.75	19.51	6.75	3.68
6	568	80.31	5.83	3.27	7.33	3.27	198.96	14.44	8.10	18.16	8.10	4.42
Experiment B :												
7	504	80.32	5.32	0.82	12.72	0.82	199.00	13.18	2.04	31.51	2.04	1.11
8	509	80.15	5.32	0.99	12.55	0.99	198.59	13.18	2.45	31.10	2.45	1.34
9	526	79.53	5.32	1.61	11.93	1.61	197.04	13.18	4.00	29.55	4.00	2.18
10	542	78.83	5.32	2.32	11.23	2.32	195.31	13.18	5.79	27.81	5.79	3.13
11	552	78.40	5.32	2.74	10.80	2.74	194.24	13.18	6.80	16.75	6.80	3.71
12	565	77.83	5.32	3.31	10.23	3.31	192.85	13.18	8.19	25.33	8.19	4.47
Experiment C :												
13	508	78.44	5.20	1.06	14.24	1.06	194.35	12.88	2.62	35.29	2.62	1.43
14	515	78.21	5.20	1.29	14.01	1.29	193.77	12.88	3.20	34.71	3.20	1.75
15	527	77.72	5.20	1.78	13.52	1.78	192.57	12.88	4.41	33.50	4.41	2.40
16	540	77.16	5.20	2.34	12.96	2.34	191.17	12.88	5.81	32.10	5.81	3.17
17	551	76.66	5.20	2.84	12.46	2.84	189.95	12.88	7.03	30.88	7.03	3.83
18	571	75.83	5.20	3.67	11.63	3.67	187.88	12.88	9.09	28.82	9.09	4.96
Experiment D :												
19	505	75.00	4.92	1.14	17.80	1.14	185.84	12.19	2.82	44.11	2.82	1.54
20	515	74.64	4.92	1.50	17.44	1.50	184.94	12.19	3.71	43.21	3.71	2.02
21	533	73.87	4.92	2.27	16.67	2.27	183.04	12.19	5.62	41.31	5.62	3.06
22	542	73.48	4.92	2.66	16.28	2.66	182.07	12.19	6.58	40.34	6.58	3.59
23	556	72.89	4.92	3.25	15.69	3.25	180.60	12.19	8.06	38.87	8.06	4.39
24	571	72.25	4.92	3.89	15.05	3.89	179.01	12.19	9.64	37.28	9.64	5.26
Experiment E :												
25	489	69.94	6.59	1.13	21.21	1.13	173.30	16.33	2.79	52.56	2.79	1.52
26	510	69.55	6.59	1.52	20.82	1.52	172.33	16.33	3.76	51.59	3.76	2.05
27	520	69.13	6.59	1.94	20.40	1.94	171.28	16.33	4.81	50.54	4.81	2.62
28	534	68.48	6.59	2.59	19.75	2.59	169.67	16.33	6.42	48.93	6.42	3.50
29	546	68.00	6.59	3.07	19.27	3.07	168.48	16.33	7.61	47.74	7.61	4.15
30	566	67.17	6.59	3.90	18.44	3.90	166.42	16.33	9.67	45.68	9.67	5.27

ZnO crystallites did not change the size (55 Å). These results agreed to those of chemisorption studies. Alumina was in a state of high dispersion, a mixture of γ and θ -Al₂O₃. If R denote crystalline/amorphous ratio, then $R = 2.77$ for unreduced catalyst and $R = 2.80$ for the reduced one, which means that the crystallinity slightly increases during reduction and will continue to increase, to a greater extent, when the catalyst ages.

The electron microscope study showed that the three oxides, CuO, ZnO and Al₂O₃, formed an almost homogeneous

mixture with particles of average size 100–200 Å. The pore radii of the catalyst was of the same order of magnitude. After catalyst reduction the metallic copper formed turns into very fine crystallites (about 60 Å) dispersed on zinc oxide (crystallized) and (amorphous) alumina. The pore size did not change essentially compared to unreduced catalyst.

In reduced state, the catalyst behaves as an electrical conductor, while in unreduced state as a semiconductor. Its electric conductivity is influenced by sodium ions (impurity which originates in the substances employed in preparation

of the catalyst) and increases with their concentration⁸.

Kinetic data : The kinetic data of the reverse water-gas shift reaction were determined with a perfectly stirred heterogeneous catalytic reactor⁹.

Two cubic centimeters of Cu-ZnO-Al₂O₃ catalyst (1.83 g, granulation 1.25–1.6 mm size) was placed in the fixed basket of the reactor. At this catalyst granulation the limitations originating in internal diffusion are eliminated. The stirrer was run continuously at 2600 rpm during catalyst activation (reduction) and the tests carried out to obtain the kinetic data; thus the perfect stirring condition was ensured⁹. The catalyst activation consisted of copper oxide reduction to metallic copper. Because the copper crystals increase their size as a result of the smallest deviation from the activation program, a mild program was chosen, similar to that employed in the industrial process.

The gas stream composition was 0.5% hydrogen in nitrogen. Temperature was increased with 60 K h⁻¹ from room temperature to 453 K. A 10 h maintaining at 453 K in gas current containing 0.5% hydrogen followed then, at 453 K as well, hydrogen concentration was increased to 1% and was maintained for 4 h in the conditions mentioned. Temperature was then raised to 483 K and maintained for 4 h. At the same temperature (483 K), the concentration of hydrogen in nitrogen was increased to 10% and reduction continued 4 h more. After reduction termination, temperature was lowered to 433 K in nitrogen atmosphere with 10% hydrogen and, at the same temperature, the reduction gas was gradually replaced with working gas.

In order to reach a constant activity throughout the testing time, the stabilization of the catalyst was carried out; temperature was increased at a rate of 20 K h⁻¹ up to 553 K and maintained at this temperature for 8 h in working gas atmosphere; it was then lowered again to 453 K to carry out the measurements. In the reaction under study, nitrogen is an inert gas; yet it may be used in regulating the molar flow rates of the other gases.

The activity tests were effected in five experiments (A-E), and in each experiment the composition of reactor feed gas was constant. The concentration of carbon dioxide ranged within 10.60–22.34% and that of hydrogen 83.57–71.07%

according to Table 6. The overall flow rate of the feed gas in all experiments was 6 dm³ h⁻¹, while working temperatures ranged 498–571 K. The analysis of gases, before and after reaction, was performed by gas chromatography (gas chromatograph Fisons Instruments 8000) after at least 1 h from the establishing of the steady state of the catalytic process. The compositions of gases after reaction in runs A-E, each run consisting of six measurements, are listed in Table 7. The same table also lists the reaction rates in moles of carbon dioxide transformed in 1 h per g of catalyst.

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